

PIC GENE IN *ESCHERICHIA COLI* ISOLATES CAUSING SUBCLINICAL MASTITIS IN GOATS

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Abstract

Escherichia coli are a common cause of intra-mammary infection in dairy cattle and goat breeds. The present study was to explore the presence of pic gene, an autotransporter serine protease, which is attributed to virulence, in the milks of goats suffering from subclinical mastitis. The study included screening of 1312 milk samples of Sirohi, Barbari, Black Bengal, Jamnapari and some non-descript breeds of goats in and around of Jabalpur region. Approximately 5 ml of milk and MCMT reagent was added in a plastic paddle, giving gentle swirling motion in a horizontal plane with minimum agitation. The reaction was graded by intensity of gel formation and colour changes and 376 positive samples on the basis of MCMT were cultured for growth of *E.coli*. There were 79 samples positive for *E.coli* species and were subjected to PCR using pic specific primers. Among the 79 isolates, 32.91% samples were positive for pic gene. These isolates were screened for six antibiotic agents in *in-vitro* condition and one of the isolate was found to be multidrug resistant. The study indicated the presence pic gene, a factor attributed to virulence in the *E.coli* species.

Key words: Subclinical mastitis, *E.coli*, pic gene.

Introduction

Mastitis remains one of the most common diseases of the dairy goats, a cause for major economic loss. Targeting antimicrobial treatment of animal infections such as mastitis against causal agent is generally recommended, but this is only possible with identification of the causal bacteria in the milk samples.

Escherichia coli are common cause of intramammary infection in dairy cattle and goats. Infection usually manifests with clinical signs. Epidemiological data and early strain typing studies showed large heterogeneity among isolates associated with cases of mastitis within farms (Nemeth *et al.*, 1994; Lipman *et al.*, 1995; Lam *et al.*, 1996). There are no specific virulence factors that differentiate strains with the ability to cause mastitis from other *Escherichia coli* strains (Wenz *et al.*, 2006; Suojala *et al.*, 2011). So, it is important to identify the virulence factors of isolated organisms from mastitis. Autotransporter proteins (AT) are associated with bacterial virulence attributes. Originally identified in entero aggregative *Escherichia coli* (EAEC), *Shigella flexneri* 2a and uropathogenic *E. coli*, the serine protease Pic is one of these AT (Afonso *et al.*, 2016). The virulence factor that enable *E. coli* to evade the immune system is the protein involved

in colonization (Pic), is a serine protease of 116 kDa secreted via the type V secretion pathway (Eslava, 1993; Abreu, 2016).

Clinical microbiologists have traditionally been involved in isolation of bacteria in pure culture and performing biochemical or immunological tests for detection of *Escherichia coli*. These tests are labour intensive and time consuming and may give false negative results due to presence of residual antibiotics. It is only possible with identification of the causal bacteria in the milk samples. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is the most acknowledged and adaptable DNA-based assay technique partly due to the amplification of target DNA sequence by, as much as five orders of magnitude, reducing or eliminating the lengthy enrichment and isolation of micro-organisms (Hill 1996; Barrett *et al.*, 1997). The present study was to explore the presence of pic gene, an autotransporter serine protease, which is attributed to virulence, in the milks of goats suffering from subclinical mastitis.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Total of 1312 milk samples from functional halves of lactating goats in an Central Indian urban city, Jabalpur (23.1815° N, 79.9864° E) were screened for udder health status. Milk samples (5ml) were collected in sterile tubes for bacterial isolation and identification, respectively. The samples were transferred in cold chain to the laboratory for further processing.

Bacterial isolation and characterization of *Escherichia coli* spp. in positive milk samples

Goat milk samples showing +2 (distinct positive) and +3 (strong positive) or more reaction in MCMT were cultured bacteriologically to isolate and identify the *Escherichia coli* bacteria. For the isolation of *Escherichia coli*, milk samples (1 ml) was inoculated into the 5 ml of MacConkey's broth and incubated aerobically at 37°C for 18-24 hour for primary enrichment.

After primary enrichment the culture was streaked on MacConkey agar medium and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The suspected *Escherichia coli* colonies from MacConkey agar was streaked on EMB (Eosin Methylene Blue) agar plate and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Based on 'green metallic sheen' colony morphology the organism was confirmed as *Escherichia coli* following biochemical and Gram's staining properties (Cruikshank *et al.*, 1975).

Antibiotic sensitivity profile of *E. coli* carrying Pic gene

The antimicrobial sensitivity of the *Escherichia coli* isolates having pic gene was investigated using disk diffusion method as described by National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS, 1997). Biochemically characterized *Escherichia coli* isolates having pic gene were tested for sensitivity against different antibiotics including cefepime (30 mcg), ampicillin+ sulbactam (10/10 mcg), enrofloxacin (10 mcg), ciprofloxacin (5 mcg), erythromycin (15mcg), tetracycline (30mg) following the procedure described by Bauer *et al.*, (1966). A suspension of the test organism was prepared in sterile saline equivalent to 0.5 McFarland turbidity standards and incubated at 37°C for 2 hours. With the help of sterile cotton swab the culture was inoculated on Mueller Hinton agar plate and spread evenly over entire surface while using a sterile forceps

antimicrobial disks were placed over the agar surface at an equal distance from each other and plates incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Diameter of bacterial inhibition zone around each applied disc was measured. Bacterial isolates showing no inhibition zone around the antibiotic disc used and well-developed colonies within the zone were rechecked against same drug for confirmation of resistance based on CLSI, 2015.

Amplification of *pic* gene of *E. coli*

For the identification of *Escherichia coli* carrying *pic* marker gene, DNA was extracted by using DNeasy® Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen GmbH, Hilden, Germany) PCR was carried out for amplification of by using specific Forward primers 5' ATTCTTCTGGCTGGCATTCC3' and Reverse primers 5'CGGGATTAGAGACTATTGTTGC3' (Shivairo *et al.*, 2013). The *Escherichia coli* (MTCC- 448) was used as standard and 79 isolates of *Escherichia coli* species from subclinical mastitis were subjected to PCR for amplification of *pic* marker gene. The usual cyclic conditions were initial denaturation at 95°C for 10 minutes, cyclic denaturation at 95°C for 1 minute annealing at 55°C for 30 seconds and extension at 72 for 30 sec for 30 cycles followed the final extension of 72°C for 7 minutes. The PCR product was resolved in 1.5% agarose gel and viewed in UV transilluminator system.

Results

Out of total 376 samples, *E. coli* were positive for 21%. The colonies were bright pink colored, large and non-mucoid on MacConkey agar (Fig.1 a) and had 'green metallic sheen' colony morphology EMB (Eosin Methylene Blue) agar plate (Fig1 b).

Fig. 1a: Pink colour colonies of *Escherichia coli* in MacConkey agar

Fig. 1b: Green metallic sheen colonies of *Escherichia coli* in EMB agar

All the bacterial isolates showed red layer at the top of the tube after the addition of Kovács reagent indicated positive Indole test and positive methyl red test was indicated by the development of red color after the addition of methyl red reagent, negative Voges Proskauer test was indicated by lack of color change after the addition of Barritt's A and Barritt's B reagents and negative citrate utilization test was indicated by the lack of growth and color change in the tube (Fig.2a). All the isolates had rod shaped colonies on grams staining (Fig.2b).

Fig. 2a: IMVIC test for identification of *Escherichia coli*

Fig. 2b: Gram negative rod shaped *Escherichia coli* at 1000X magnification

Antibacterial activity of *Escherichia coli* specie isolates carrying *pic* gene

Antimicrobial activity of different chemotherapeutic agents against the isolates of *Escherichia coli* spp. Carrying *pic* gene (26 isolates) was investigated. The average zone of inhibition of different antibiotic agents was shown in table 01. There was single isolate which showed resistant towards Ampicillin + Sulbactam, Erythromycin, tetracycline and intermediately sensitive towards ciprofloxacin.

Table 01: Antibiogram for *Escherichia coli* isolates as per the zone of inhibition

S. No.	Antibiotic	Zone of inhibition (Average)(mm)
1.	Cefepime (30 mcg)	13.41
2.	Ampicillin+ sulbactam (10/10 mcg)	10.25
3.	Enrofloxacin (10 mcg)	23.25
4.	Ciprofloxacin (5 mcg)	20.5
5.	Erythromycin	10.00
6.	Tetracycline	11.00

Fig. 3: Antibiotic Sensitivity profile of a *E.coli* isolate having *Pic* gene showing resistance against Ampicillin + Salbactum, Erythromycin, tetracycline

PCR for amplification of *pic* marker gene

The PCR for amplification of *pic* marker gene of *Escherichia coli* was indicated by 576 bp (approximately) fragment in agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig 4). The occurrences of *pic* gene among the *E.coli* isolates were found to be 32.91%.

Fig. 4: Amplification of *pic* marker gene in positive control and negative control samples for standardization

Lane M	:	100 bp DNA ladder
Lane 1 and 2	:	Amplified product of <i>pic</i> marker gene in positive control samples
Lane 3	:	Negative control sample

Discussion

As sub-clinical mastitis is less obvious and detectable only by measures of milk's cellular content, it is 15-40 times more prevalent than the clinical form (Shearer *et al.*, 2003). This is a concern among producers and veterinarians as there are no visible signs of the disease, which can eventually develop into the chronic clinical form of mastitis. Subclinical mastitis in goats is mainly of bacterial origin (Bergonier *et al.* 2003). In the present study, *E. coli* was isolated from 79 milk samples among the 376 milk samples with MCMT Scores of 2 or 3 are indicative of mastitis. Danmaliyam & Pimenoc (2019) reported isolation of *E.coli* (15.5%) from milks having clinical mastitis.

The ubiquitous nature of *E.coli* makes the differentiation of pathogenic from non pathogenic ones difficult. Virulence factors (VF) related to the pathogenicity of Extra intestinal Pathogenic E coli (ExPEC) are numerous and have a wide range of activities, from those related to colonization to those including adhesins, toxins, iron acquisition factors, lipopolysaccharides, polysaccharide capsules, and invasins, which are usually encoded on pathogenicity islands (PAIs), plasmids and other mobile genetic elements. The different biological roles for *Pic* protein have been assigned, including mucinolytic activity, hemagglutination, coagulation cascade factor V degradation, and leukocyte surface glycoprotein cleavage (Abreu *et al.*, 2016). In the present study, 32.91% isolates were found to be carrying *pic* gene which is comparable to the report of Shivairo *et al.* (2013). They observed that 37.5% of mastitis causing *Escherichia coli* in goats was found to be carrying *pic* gene. Though non of the goats in the present study had history of diarrhea, David *et al.*, (2016) associated *pic* genes with incidences of persistent diarrhea in Peruvian children. All the *E.coli* isolates had usual biochemical characters and staining properties.

Pic-producing pathogens are able to destroy the protective barrier of the epithelium causing bacterial persistence, invasion, migration to extra-intestinal sites, and some of them have the capacity to reach the bloodstream, causing bacteremia and sepsis (Herzok *et al.*, 2014). In the present study, milk was collected from the suspected udder and the isolation of *E.coli* having *pic* gene indicates invasion and migration to epithelium in the affected udder. It may be inferred from the present study that milk consumption from goat having subclinical mastitis is of public health concern that such *E.coli* having *pic* gene may induce persistent diarrhea among human beings.

All isolates were sensitive in *in-vitro* conditions towards the antibiotic agents used in the study except one isolate which showed resistance towards more than one antibiotic. The indiscriminate and frequent use of these antibiotics in animals could be the reason for their ineffectiveness. Microbial resistance to antibiotics is a worldwide problem in human and veterinary medicine. Commonly, the principal risk factor for an increase in this situation is the extensive use of

antibiotics leading to the dissemination of resistant bacteria and resistance genes in animals and humans (Van den Bogaard & Stobberingh, 2000).

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